

Developing the Creativity of Future Primary School Teachers

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Currently, the main goal of higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to contribute to the development of society by training competitive and highly qualified personnel. Cooperation between education, science, and industry is considered a crucial factor in preparing such specialists.

In modern pedagogy, the concept of “creativity” has begun to be widely applied. The growing need to establish innovative and creative approaches in the teaching process has led to the emergence of “Creative Pedagogy” as an independent subject among pedagogical disciplines. The foundations of this subject are based on the methodological ideas of the history of pedagogy, general and vocational pedagogy, psychology, methodology of teaching specific subjects, educational technology, and professional ethics. The general principles of the “Creative Pedagogy” course serve to create the necessary conditions for the professional development of specialists, including future professionals. Therefore, developing the creativity of future primary school teachers is considered one of the pressing issues in “Creative Pedagogy.”

The professional formation and development of a person as a specialist, by its nature, is manifested as a process. Professional maturity begins with the establishment of ideas about professional development during important periods of human ontogenesis (ages 14–17) and continues until the completion of professional activity (ages 55–60). The formation and development of a creative individual depend on the harmony between internal and external changes, socio-economic conditions, and the activity content that requires continuity and succession from birth to the end of life.

It is known that professional experience is reflected as the integration of knowledge, skills, and competencies. However, mastering professional and creative activity skills requires not only integrating practical knowledge and methods for organizing professional activity but also being aware of the methodology of professional creativity, developing creative thinking, and sufficiently acquiring personal qualities of a creative nature.

Despite the substantial practical work being done, many teachers still do not have experience in effectively developing creativity in themselves and their students.

The education management bodies focus each year on achieving higher efficiency in educational institutions. For this purpose, curricula are developed and new textbooks are created. This helps both students and teachers in their professional growth. The undertaken practical efforts foster in students a desire to succeed and strive forward, aiding in the development of their cognitive abilities.

However, by the end of the academic year, many higher education institutions still do not observe significant positive results in students’ mastery of subjects. Many students have lost interest in learning. As a result, teachers also no longer approach their professional activities with the same enthusiasm.

Although education management bodies are developing new measures to change the behavior of students who lack motivation for learning and teachers who are reluctant to teach such students, the situation remains unchanged.

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What is the reason for this? Perhaps lessons being planned in advance are not engaging for students. Perhaps the content of education, being limited to certain templates, provides no incentive or encouragement for students. Abandoning pre-planned lessons and instead fostering critical and creative thinking in students — compelling them to think creatively and generate new ideas — would be a key factor in changing attitudes toward learning and motivating students to achieve success. The missing element in most lessons is creativity.

To fully understand the essence of the process of developing creativity in future primary school teachers, it is first necessary to comprehend the meaning of the term “creativity.” According to Ken Robinson, “creativity is a set of original ideas that have value” (Azzam, 2009). Gardner describes the concept as “a practical activity carried out by an individual, which must reflect novelty and have certain practical value.” From the perspective of E. Mebane (1989), creativity means “having deep knowledge in a specific field along with highly original skills.”

Various studies offer differing views on the relationship between intelligence and creativity. Some researchers claim there is no connection, while others assert that creativity and the level of intelligence are interrelated (Kim, 2005).

In modern education, several pedagogical research methods can be used to form and develop the creativity of future primary school teachers.

The Interview Method

During pedagogical observation, this method helps enrich the student’s knowledge about creativity, assess situations correctly, find solutions to problems, and engage the subjects of experimental work in solving issues. Interviews can be conducted individually, in groups, or publicly. It is important to ensure that students’ creative potential is fully expressed during the interview.

Pedagogical Analysis

The purpose of using this method in research is to determine the level of students’ acquisition of creative qualities, capabilities, and competencies. It serves to theoretically substantiate the validity of the idea proposed by the pedagogue.

Pedagogical-Psychological Diagnostic Methods

These methods help assess and diagnose the student’s possession of creative qualities and skills in organizing creative activity. Nowadays, dozens of methods are used to assess whether future primary school teachers have creative qualities and skills for organizing creative activities. Among them, several practically effective methods are widely used in developed foreign countries. These include the Guilford Model, Slosson Test, Wechsler Scales (WPPSI Test), Stanford Test designed for elementary education, and Torrance Tests (including the Incomplete Figures Test).

Pedagogical Experiment (Latin: “experiment” – “to try out”)

This method is used to study possibilities for solving problems, evaluate whether existing pedagogical conditions can ensure goal achievement, assess the practical reflection of given recommendations, and determine their effectiveness. There are several types of pedagogical experiments. When conducting them, special attention should be paid to ensuring their effectiveness. At the end of the experiment, general conclusions are drawn based on the results obtained, and scientific-methodical recommendations are developed.

The Method of Studying Students’ Creative Work

This method is used to determine students’ abilities, talents, and knowledge level in specific subject areas. Students’ creative work — such as two-page diaries, essays, written tasks, short essays,

reports, course projects, graduation theses, and teaching practice reports — serve as important tools. This method helps recognize, evaluate, and develop the unique potential of each student.

Developing the creativity of future primary school teachers requires educators to possess a high level of professional competence, skills, and abilities. A creative approach by educators to the educational process fosters students' interest in learning and helps activate their cognitive activities. Moreover, it creates the necessary conditions for students to fully acquire creative qualities, skills, and competencies as future professionals and effectively develop their creative activity capabilities.

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